

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B242
Date: 28 August 2006
Take Off 11:02:43
Landing: 15:33:38
Flight Time 4h30m55s

Campaign: DODO

Operating Area: Over ocean areas off the coast of Senegal/Mauritania

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission scientist 2	Clare Allen	Leeds University
7	Mission scientist 3	Mark Harrison	Met Office
8	Filters PSAP	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
9	SWS	Claire McConnell	Reading University
10	GRIMM	Paul Williams	Manchester University
11	AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
12	Core Chem	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B242 Track 28-AUG-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b242
 Date: 28 aug 2006
 Project: DODO
 Location: Dakar

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094907		XR5M	0.05 kft	336	14'44.61N 17'29.45W
102450		INU	0.04 kft	336	to nav
102727		CGPS	0.04 kft	336	b242cgps.log
105257		ASP	0.05 kft	105	open
105336		psap	0.05 kft	105	flow on
110243		T/O	0.04 kft	352	Dakar
110243	112542	Profile 1	0.41 - 21.0 kft	333	from t/o
110331		bbr	0.75 kft	294	retract
110347		heimann	0.92 kft	292	shutter open
110427		psap	1.2 kft	288	flow on at t/o
110509		Video	2.0 kft	290	#1 Ufc #2 Dfc starte
112543	113558	Profile 2	21.0 - 12.5 kft	001	
113558	115942	Run 1.1	12.5 kft	004	
113639		heimann	12.5 kft	004	cal 10
113657		nev	12.5 kft	005	zero
113751		JW	12.5 kft	006	zero
115942	121241	Profile 3	12.5 - 0.03 kft	006	
121242	123415	Profile 4	0.04 - 21.0 kft	354	
121317		P4	0.29 kft	351	turn in profile
121625		qnh	2.8 kft	091	1017
123435		!	21.0 kft	114	manouver
123516		CO	21.0 kft	179	cal
123652		video	21.0 kft	182	#3 Ufc #4 Dfc start
123836	125809	Profile 5	21.0 - 5.0 kft	181	
125810	130712	Run 2.1	5.0 kft	181	
130713	131915	Profile 6	5.0 - 18.0 kft	180	
131931		Sonde 1	18.0 kft	179	
131950		!	18.0 kft	179	manouvre
132449	133724	Profile 7	18.0 - 5.0 kft	017	
133725	135656	Profile 8	5.0 - 18.0 kft	011	
133914		p8	6.4 kft	009	interrupted
133914	134606	Run 3.1	6.4 kft	003	
134606		p8	7.4 kft	003	resumed
135705		Sonde2	18.0 kft	003	
135713	140732	Run 4.1	18.0 kft	003	
140747	142849	Profile 9	17.9 - 5.0 kft	357	
140957		Video	16.0 kft	357	#5 Ufc #6 Dfc
141324		p9	13.0 kft	357	interrupted
141909		p9	13.0 kft	189	resumed
143009	144747	Profile 10	5.0 - 22.0 kft	184	
144747	145725	Profile 11	22.0 - 12.0 kft	184	
145725	151928	Run 5.1	12.0 kft	179	
151929	153337	Profile 12	12.0 - 0.09 kft	182	
151948	153338	p12	11.7 kft	182	down to land
153338		Land	0.09 kft	351	Dakar
154014		XR5M	0.11 kft	153	14'44.66N 17'29.43W

B242 Track 28-AUG-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO2: in-situ sampling and radiometric measurements of mineral dust

Flight No: B242

Date: 28 August 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of mineral dust and measure the radiative effects.

Location:

Over ocean areas off the coast of Senegal/Mauritania.

Point alpha = 19N, 18W.

Weather:

High loadings of dust. Cloudless skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Low-level (50ft) flying over ocean.

60 degree banked orbits at 600ft.

2 dropsondes required.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar at 11Z.
2. From take-off perform a profile ascent to 20,000ft (or above the dust layer) at 1000ft/min in a direction towards point alpha [20mins, T=20mins].
3. Profile descent to a level determined by the mission scientist followed by a set of in-situ sampling SLRs at different altitudes [50mins, T=70mins].
4. Reciprocal turn, followed by a SLR at MPA (100ft) directly beneath the in-situ sampling runs for approximately 60minutes [60mins, T=130mins].
5. Reciprocal turn, then a profile ascent to a level determined by the mission scientist followed by a set of three in-situ sampling SLRs at different altitudes each run of 10minute duration. A 60degree banked orbit may/may not be required during this run [50mins, T=180mins].
6. Reciprocal turn, then a SLR at 20,000ft (or above the dust layer) directly above the in-situ sampling runs for approximately 40mins. A sonde should be dropped at the beginning and at the end of the run [40mins, T=220mins].
7. Profile descent to 50ft towards Dakar [10mins, T=230mins].
8. Recover to Dakar [10mins, T=240mins].

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B242

Date: 28/08/06

Sortie Objectives: Investigation of the in-situ and radiative properties over oceans.

Operating area: Oceanic areas off the coast of Senegal and Mauritania. Initially along the 18W line of longitude, followed by the 16.5W line of longitude.

Weather: A wave depression on the ITCZ had passed to the south of the region the night before the flight. There had been some precipitation in Dakar. However, the models forecast dust moving in behind the wave.

Flight Patterns: Subsequent to take off a profile ascent was performed immediately to FL210 heading in a northerly direction. The profile showed two distinct dust layers, the first from the surface to FL70, then a clear slot to FL100 and a more intense elevated dust layer from approximately FL100 to FL150. A profile descent was then performed to the middle of the upper dust layer at FL125. There were significant amounts of both Ci above (4/8) and Cu below (4/8). The run was continued to the north where the aerosol concentrations increased before a profile descent was performed to 100ft. The descent showed a peak nephelometer scattering of $100 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$ at approximately FL100 and a clear slot from FL80 to FL60 with a lower dust layer from 1000ft to FL60 and a sea-salt layer up to 1000ft. There was still significant Ci observed during this descent. An email message was received suggesting clearer skies to the east, so a turn to the east was performed on a profile ascent towards the east to FL210. The Ci and Cu cleared during this profile ascent. A profile descent was then performed to FL50. The lower external shutter on the BBRs was not used during this flight so that the SHIMS instrument could be fully utilised. Cu re-appeared from about 12:55Z. The profile down was curtailed at FL50 which was a marked clear slot above the scattered Cu below, but below the main dust layer. This run was performed for 10 minutes with upper SHIMS recording. A profile ascent from FL50 to FL180 was then performed to the south to FL180 - again this should be good for both SHIMS and SWS work. There was less aerosol to the south of the region as predicted by the model and confirmed by the OMI satellite image. The aircraft then performed a reciprocal turn to the north and a profile descent to FL50, followed by an ascent to FL180. A sonde was dropped at the north of this run. A profile descent was then performed to the south. The lower BBRs reached $\sim 120 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ indicating a significant DRE. Further profiles were performed across the dust layer before fuel meant that we turned for home.

Summary: A successful flight – the SHIMS instrument should provide a good analysis. The vertical profile of the dust showed interesting structure. Careful analysis should make BBR and SHIMS data useable.

Problems: SWS showed very patchy performance – the visible module hardly worked at all during this flight.

The nephelometer blue scattering is showing a very obvious problem – it is far too low – not sure if this is due to the flight constants being used in HORACE being old or whether it needs a recalibration.

The low pyrgeometer was U/S.

23z_270806 AOD T+18

At 12Z on 28/ 8/2006, from 18Z on 27/ 8/2006

OMI Aerosol Index
on August 28, 2006

Cloud off coast
clear behind in
Noumea channel.

Mission Scientist's Log

120
c

JMH 120
50 MH

Flight No **B**...242.....
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Date ...28/08/09.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:45z					1/8 Cu, 1/8 Ci - some rain in region T-6 to T-12. Dust forecast to the north of region. Cloud should move to west & dissipate. QNH 1021.4 mb.
11:00z					T/O
11:02:43	STP1	0 ↑			Some Cu ~ 2/8 Bottom of Cu ~ 1500ft Cloud tops ~ 2,800 ft.
10:06					Quite hazy above Some Ci above - v. thin
11:10					Cu clearing below. Sea state ~ 2 - no whitecaps.
11:16:00					Dust to 6000ft, then clear to 100FL then dust 100FL to 150FL. Extensive Ci above.
11:25:43	End P1 Start P2	FL210	1°		End P1/Start P2
11:35:58	End P2 Start P1	FL125	4°	16°42', 18W	4/8 Ci above 4/8 Cu below

Mission Scientist's Log

JMH

Flight No **B**.....242.....

Date28/08/09.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:53					Some more mid-level cloud directly ahead
11:56				18°12'N, 18W	Neph increasing here to $50 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ ^{$\times 10^{-6}$}
11:59:42	End R11 St P3	FL125 ↓	4°	18°30'N, 18W	Email suggests offset to E to try & get clear skies.
					<u>Neph</u>
					FL150
					FL100
					FL080
					FL060 ← clear slot.
					100ft
					← sea salt
					Lots of structure.
12:12:41	End P3 St P4	100ft ↑	1°	19°24', 18W	Displace by 2° to E. A turn to the east.
					Dust looking good to $100 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$.
				19°30'N, 17W	Ci cleared here. Should use for radiation.
12:34:15	End P4 St P4	210ft ↑			
12:38:36	St P5	210ft ↓		19°6', 16W	30° Clear from Cu until 12:55
12:55:					Some Cu starting.

Mission Scientist's Log

JMH

Flight No **B**...242....

Date 28/08/09.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	End P5	FL50 →			
12:58:09	St R2	FL50 →	181	17°14'21"N 16°36'W	Scattered Cu below. In clear slot at FL50.
					340°, 10 knts wind Nouakchott.
13:07:12	End P1 St P6	FL50 →	180	17°1', 16°42'	Markedly different profile → less aerosol in the south, more in the north.
					Only very little Air-Ci.
					→ shouldn't affect SWS/ SHIMS
					→ coast to LHS.
13:19:15	End R	FL180			— " —
13:19:51	End R	FL180	180	16°18' 16°42'	Dropsonde #1. Reciprocal turn.
13:24:39	Start Profile	FL180	9	18°N 16°W	Down to 5000ft. Peak at 38m ⁻¹ - 40m ⁻¹
13:31					O3 dropping peak 76m ⁻¹ 12500ft
13:32					Dust dropping off at 10500
13:34			11	17°6'N 16°36'W	peak 68m ⁻¹ 7800 ft
13:37	Start Prof 8		11	17,10N 1636W	
13:39:40	Pause Prof 8	(interrupted) Run 31	10	17 24 N 16 30 W.	
13:46:06	Prof 8	65 → FL180	2	17.48N, 16.30 W	
13:50					Preparing sonde drop P10 sheet ①
13:50:27	End of Prof 8	FL180		18.42 N 1636W	Drop sonde gone (13.57.05). SWS x SHIMS ✓
13:57:13	Start of Run (10)	FL180			Dust visible below ground 17.04.50.

Mission Scientist's Log

JMH

Flight No **B...242...**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:07:32 14:07:47	End R10 Start P9	FL180	357	19°36'/16°36'	Dust layer below. Light cirrus NNE
14:11:	Int P9	FL130	357	19°54'/16°30'	Entering dust - neph shading up to 290 m ⁻¹
14:19:09	Restart P9	FL130	189	19°42'16°41'	Dust thick here.
					Lower BBRs reads 120 Wm ⁻²
					over ocean → highest
					DRE seen of ~ 70 Wm ⁻²
14:28:49	End P9	FL50	184	19°6'/16°48'	
14:30:09	St P10	FL50	184		Low on fuel → start profile.
					No Cu / No Ci
					Good for radiation work.
					Lower red BBR showing
					some anticorrelation
					14:30 - 14:35
14:40:00					A little Ci, but mainly
					clear - swap SHIMS to
					look down.
14:43					Lower BBRs ~ 90 Wm ⁻²
					Cu start shortly after.
					SHIMS is looking down
					only good until 14:43.
14:47:47	End/St P10/P11	FL220	183	17°42'/17°W	Descend into dust layer
					at FL120
					Top of dust at ~ FL140
14:57:25	End P11 St RST	FL120	179	17°0'/17°6'	
15:14:00					Accelerate a little to expediate.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B242

Date: 28/08/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:30:00	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time: +	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:03:07																Start Profile 1 from take -off	
11:05:12	240	0.08		20												FL020	
11:06:26	175	0.08		10												FL030	
11:07:35	230	0.08		10												FL040	
11:08:41	220	0.08		10												FL050	
11:09:42	115	0.09		10												FL060	
11:11:01	50	0.07		5												FL070 Heaters on	
11:12:02	40	0.08		5												FL080	
11:13:22	20*	0.07		5												FL090	
11:14:27	40*	0.10		20												FL100	
11:15:40	100*	0.10		20												FL110	
11:16:51	100*	0.10		15												FL120	
11:17:59	60*	0.10		15												FL130	
11:19:15	20*	0.10		10												FL140	
11:20:15	20*	0.08		5												FL150	
11:21:08	5*	0.06		2												FL160	
11:22:01	5*	0.06		2												FL170	
11:22:53	5*	0.06		2												FL180	
11:23:47	5*	0.06		1												FL190	
11:24:45	5*	0.06		1												FL200	
11:25:45	5*	0.05		1												End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 from FL210	
11:26:50	5*	0.06		1												FL200	
11:28:03	5*	0.06														FL190	
11:29:10	5*	0.06		1												FL180	
11:30:18	5*	0.06		2												FL170	
11:31:31	5*	0.06		5												FL160	
11:33:30	30*	0.06		10												FL150	
11:34:14	30*	0.08		15												FL140	
11:35:58	80*	0.07		15												End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ FL125	
11:36:00	70*	0.07		15													
11:38:00	50*	0.07		15													
11:40:00	40*	0.07		15													
11:42:00	40*	0.07		10													
11:44:00	40*	0.08		10													
11:46:00	40*	0.08		10													
11:48:00	50*	0.08		10													
11:50:00	50*	0.08		15													
11:52:00	50*	0.09		20													
11:54:00	50*	0.09		30													
11:56:00	50*	0.08		30													
11:58:00	50*	0.09		70													
11:59:40																End of Run 1.1 & Start Profile 3 from FL125	
12:00:15	50*	0.10		60												FL120	
12:01:17	60*	0.10		100												FL110	
12:02:14	100*	0.11		100												FL100	
12:03:15	100*	0.09		80												FL090	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B242

Date: 28/08/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:30:00	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time: +	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:04:28	120*	0.08		50												FL080	
12:05:18	20*	0.06		5												FL070	
12:06:19	20*	0.06		5												FL060	
12:07:07	70*	0.06		5												FL050	
12:07:58	90*	0.07		5												FL040	
12:08:54	180	0.08		5												FL030	
12:09:54	120	0.08		5												FL020	
12:10:49	140	0.09		80												FL010	
12:12:35	220	0.08		10												End of Profile 3 & start Profile 4 @ 50'	
12:14:20	35	0.08		5												FL010	
12:15:42	100	0.09		5												FL020	
12:16:40	60	0.09		5												FL030	
12:17:32	45	0.09		5												FL040	
12:18:31	40	0.10		10												FL050	
12:19:33	55	0.09		10												FL060	
12:20:35	10	0.10		5												FL070	
12:21:44	115	0.12		90												FL080	
12:22:43	135	0.16		100												FL090	
12:23:48	120	0.15		90												FL100	
12:24:51	120	0.15		80												FL110	
12:25:53	100	0.14		80												FL120	
12:26:47	100	0.15		70												FL130	
12:27:49	70	0.16		50												FL140	
12:28:47	30*	0.11		10												FL150	
12:29:50	10*	0.10		10												FL160	
12:30:46	10*	0.10		5												FL170	
12:31:35	5*	0.07														FL180	
12:32:32	5*	0.06														FL190	
12:33:19	5*	0.06														FL200	
12:34:13	5*	0.06														End of Profile 4 @ FL210	
12:38:37	5*	0.06														Start Profile 5 from FL210	
12:39:38	5*	0.06														FL200	
12:40:51	5*	0.06														FL190	
12:42:04	5*	0.06		1												FL180	
12:43:16	5*	0.06		2												FL170	
12:44:30	10*	0.07		5												FL160	
12:45:54	10*	0.07		10												FL150	
12:47:22	80*	0.09		90												FL140	
12:48:27	70*	0.09		100												FL130	
12:49:30	130*	0.11		100												FL120	
12:50:37	140*	0.09		100												FL110	
12:51:40	140*	0.09		100												FL100	
12:52:59	140*	0.09		90												FL090	
12:54:00	120*	0.11		90												FL080	
12:55:23	100*	0.08		50												FL070	
12:56:47	80*	0.08		10												FL060	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B242

Date: 28/08/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:30:00	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time: +	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:58:08																End of Profile 5 & start Run 2.1 @ FL050	
12:59:00	10*	0.10		5													
13:01:00	10*	0.10		2													
13:03:00	5*	0.09		2													
13:05:00	5*	0.09		2													
13:07:11																End of Run 2.1 & Start Profile 6 from FL050	
13:08:15	30	0.10		5												FL060	
13:09:15	70	0.13		30												FL070	
13:10:03	130	0.13		60												FL080	
13:10:58	140	0.13		10												FL090	
13:12:00	160	0.10		10												FL100	
13:12:58	115	0.09		10												FL110	
13:13:45	90	0.13		70												FL120	
13:14:35	100	0.12		50												FL130	
13:15:26	30*	0.10		10												FL140	
13:16:25	10*	0.10		10												FL150	
13:17:17	20*	0.08		10												FL160	
13:18:14	5*	0.07		5												FL170	
13:19:14	5*	0.06		2												End of Profile 6 @ FL180	
13:24:47	5*	0.06		2												Start Profile 7 from FL180	
13:25:46	5*	0.06		2												FL170	
13:26:45	10*	0.07		5												FL160	
13:27:39	15*	0.07		10												FL150	
13:28:34	30*	0.09		50												FL140	
13:29:35	50*	0.09		100												FL130	
13:30:32	100*	0.09		80												FL120	
13:31:33	140*	0.08		10												FL110	
13:32:32	130*	0.08		10												FL100	
13:33:33	140*	0.08		10												FL090	
13:34:32	140*	0.10		80												FL080	
13:35:25	110*	0.08		10												FL070	
13:36:22	20*	0.08		5												FL060	
13:37:21	20*	0.08		5												End of Profile & Start Profile 8 from FL050	
13:38:28	15*	0.08		5												FL060	
13:39:14																Hold @ FL065 & start Run 3.1	
13:40:00	10*	0.08		5													
13:42:00	10*	0.08		5													
13:44:00	10*	0.08		5													
13:45:02																End of Run 3.1 & Re-Start Profile 8	
13:45:55	120	0.12		80												FL070	
13:46:44	140	0.12		70												FL080	
13:47:40	125	0.14		60												FL090	
13:48:35	110	0.14		80												FL100	
13:49:30	110	0.16		90												FL110	
13:50:29	100*	0.16		100												FL120	
13:51:31	120*	0.15		90												FL130	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B242

Date: 28/08/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:30:00	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time: +	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:52:36	60*	0.15		30												FL140	
13:53:40	10*	0.11		10												FL150	
13:54:44	5*	0.08		5												FL160	
13:55:49	5*	0.06		5												FL170	
13:56:55	5*	0.06		2												End of Profile 8 & start Run 4.1 @ FL180	
13:57:00	5*	0.06		2													
13:59:00	5*	0.06		1													
14:01:00	5*	0.06		1													
14:03:00	5*	0.06		1													
14:05:00	5*	0.06		1													
14:07:00	5*	0.06		2													
14:07:31																End of Run 4.1 & Start Profile 9 from FL180	
14:08:42	5*	0.06		5												FL170	
14:09:58	10*	0.06		10												FL160	
14:11:05	20*	0.06		10												FL150	
14:12:18	100*	0.09		100												FL140	
14:13:24	140*	0.09		100												FL130	
14:20:18	130*	0.10		100												FL120	
14:21:38	140*	0.10		90												FL110	
14:22:45	120*	0.11		90												FL100	
14:24:00	120*	0.12		90												FL090	
14:25:10	120*	0.10		90												FL080	
14:26:18	110*	0.09		15												FL070	
14:27:24	30*	0.07		5												FL060	
14:28:46	100*	0.09		15												End of Profile 9 @ FL050	
14:30:11	100*	0.09		15												Start Profile 10 from FL050	
14:31:10	25	0.09		10												FL060	
14:32:08	140	0.11		50												FL070	
14:33:06	120	0.14		80												FL080	
14:34:07	110*	0.14		80												FL090	
14:35:15	125*	0.15		70												FL100	
14:36:07	100*	0.15		100												FL110	
14:37:13	120*	0.15		100												FL120	
14:38:20	110*	0.14		90												FL130	
14:39:25	40*	0.13		40												FL140	
14:40:30	10*	0.10		5												FL150	
14:41:24	5*	0.09		5												FL160	
14:42:22	5*	0.08		5												FL170	
14:43:12	5*	0.08		5												FL180	
14:44:10	5*	0.08		2												FL190	
14:45:10	5*	0.08		1												FL200	
14:46:07	5*	0.08		1												FL210	
14:47:43	5*	0.06		1												End of Profile 10 & Start Profile 11 @ FL220	
14:49:22	5*	0.06		1												FL210	
14:49:56	5*	0.06		1												FL200	
14:50:48	5*	0.06		1												FL190	

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B242	Date	28/8/06	Opera tor(s)	C.McCONNELL	log page	1	of	1
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

104206			6f	100	150	Dark
104216						Rec – on ground – ZENITH. NIR only
110448						Dark
110500						Rec. High Ci above, still NIR only
110624						Dark
110635						Rec
111534						Dark
111850				100	100	Dark
111903						Rec
112204						Dark
112623				150	100	Dark
112639						Rec
112826				150	100	Dark
112843			174a	150	100	Rec – NADIR, still no VIS
114913						Dark
114934						Rec
121115						Dark – signal gone
121315				150	100	Dark
121325						Rec
124047						Dark
124049						Rec
125348			6f			Dark
125415						Rec – ZENITH – ready for SLR
125810	R2.1					
130237						Dark
130409				150	100	Dark
130421						Rec – still no VIS
132151						Dark
132208						Rec
133848			174a			Dark
133911						Rec – Nadir
143008			6f			Dark – Zenith
143036						Rec
143446				150	30	Dark
143501						Rec
143641				150	30	Dark
143655						Rec
144342			174A			Dark – Nadir
144414						Rec
145026				150	150	Dark
145040	P11					Rec. some VIS signal occasionally
145639				100	100	Dark
145659						Rec
150207						Dark
150234			6f	100	100	Rec – Zenith
153518						Dark post landing

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 242 Date: 28 August 2006

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU	Y		Probes		
XR5M GPS	Y		FFSSP		
Cruciform GPS	Y		PCASP		Y
Satcom C	Y		2D-P		Y
Satcom H	Y		2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		
De-Iced Temp	Y		SID 1		Y
Non De-Iced	Y		SID 2		
Heimann	Y		HVPS		
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		
G. Eastern	Y		CIP100		
J. Williams	Y				
Nevzorov	Y				
TWC	N				
FWVS	N		Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	
Upper Clear		Y	CCN / CNC	N	
“ Red		Y	CVI	N	
“ IR		Y			
“ shims		Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear		Y	PSAP		Y
“ Red		Y	Nephelometer		Y
“ IR		Y	Filters		Y
“ shims		y	AMS		N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS		
SWS	y	Y	2BT O3		
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		
SO2		N	Formaldehyde		
NOX		Y	ADA		
CO		Y	CPI		
ORAC			NOxy		
PAN			PTRMS		
PERCA			Bag Sampling		
WAS			Tube Sampling		

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B242

Date: 28 August 2006

Instruments

CO instrument; problems during cals

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B242:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
PSAP	No log appears to have been taken for this flight
Filters	Awaiting completed log
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
GRIMM	No log currently available

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras

3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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